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HISTORICAL OVERVIEW ON THE INFLUENCE OF ITALIANISMS IN SCIENTIFIC TERMINOLOGY IN ALBANIAN

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Abstract

This scientific research aims to highlight the influences and contact points between the Italian language and the Albanian language and will deal with a historical overview of it. We will analyze the source of borrowings and how they have been integrated into the Albanian language. The methodology followed is that of research and consultation of studies carried out in advance by Albanian and foreign linguists, as well as in the collection of the corpus of Italianisms in this field, which prove the influences that the Italian language has had on the Albanian one. In order to highlight the dynamics of the development of this lexicon, the analysis was done starting from the pre-liberation period, because this is precisely the period of crystallization of this lexicon, closely related to external factors. In this period, we can talk about an embryonic development of the mainly mechanical industry, when the first factories began to be built.

Keywords: Italian language, Albanian language, terminology, borrowings

Introduction

Relations between Albania and Italy have been established for centuries and the two countries have traveled many paths together. Italianisms are also present in other languages of the Balkans due to historical, economic, commercial, political, cultural factors. This also leads to the exchange of Balkan languages with each other, where they have influenced the penetration of Italianisms not directly, but indirectly. K.Jorgaqi³ stratifies the influence and penetration of Italianisms in two layers, in the period of the late Middle Ages (XIII - XVIII centuries) where the influence of the Venetian dialect is felt and at the end of the last century by Italian language. Since the Italian language has had an impact on the Albanian language and in many sectors, Italy has played a very important role.

A. Omari⁴ writes that "...for the historical and geographical characteristics of our country, the second language through which the impact of globalization is expressed on us is Italian... For this reason, we are not surprised by the presence of a significant number of Italianisms in the Albanian language.

Italianisms have created their own layer in the Albanian lexicon, having as a legacy the influence left by Latin, although the Latin element is distinguished from

the Italian one. The main difference is that Latin words have undergone greater changes in their phonetic form than Italian words, which are newer. Italian words have influenced both spoken and written language. Italian political and commercial interests and the continued presence of the Catholic Church marked the beginning of the introduction of Italianisms since the century XI⁵. According to Di Giovine⁶ the Albanian language has been receptive to Italianisms due to historical and cultural factors and for this reason the number of Italianisms in it has increased.⁷ While in the written language, words and terms belonging to the field of technology, science, arts, navigation, army, etc. have penetrated.

B.Dashi⁸ notes that in the Albanian language there are about 5926 borrowings from the Italian language, which have entered the Albanian language directly or indirectly, that is, through another language such as Latin or even from French. We add here the Italianisms that have entered from the Balkan languages. But we have noticed that there is a difficulty in identifying words with a direct Italian or French source, especially in the 19th century because the influence of these two languages was simultaneous and we come across words that Italian has served as an intermediate language, but as a source language it is the French. For this reason,

³ Jorgaqi K., 1995, Italianizma të shqipes standard si ballkanizma, Studime Filologjike, Akademia e Shkencave e Republikës së Shqipërisë, Instituti I Gjuhësisë dhe I Letërsisë nr 1-4, fq 69 - 73

⁴ Omari A., 2009, Vëzhgime rreth zhvillimeve të shqipes së sotme nën ndikimin e gjuhëve të huaja, Gjuha Jonë, Qendra e Studimeve Albanologjike, Instituti I Gjuhësisë dhe I Letërsisë, fq 186

⁵ Di Giovine 2008, Un millennio di storia linguistica albanee: l'influsso lessicale della lingua italiana, "L'Italia dialettale",

rivista di Dialettologia italiana, vol LXIX (Serie terza V), Pisa, Edizioni ETS: 107 – 139

⁶ Po aty fq 108 - 112

⁷ Çabej E. 1987, Hyrje në historinë e gjuhës shqipe.

Fonetika. Parashitesat-prapashtesat. Shumëzimi I singularizuar, Prishtinë, fq 57

⁸ Dashi B., 2013, Italianismi nella lingua Albanese, Edizioni Nuova Cultura, Roma

linguists have studied the linguistic structure of lexical units, semantic fields, and lexical units that belong to certain fields where they have had more influence from Italians and indicators are considered Italianisms⁹.

Italian words that have come during the '20¹⁰ in the period of the establishment of the state, they were seen by intellectuals as words of culture and civilization; then during the '30¹¹ with the invasion of Albania by the Italians, they penetrated the written language and are words, but also terms belonging to the ecclesiastical field, technology, science, art, navigation, army, economy, etc.

Results and discussion

In support of the beforementioned arguments, we present some historical facts¹², to concretize the use of Italianisms in different fields, starting from extra-linguistic factors.

Between Albania and Italy in January 1924 an agreement on trade and navigation was signed, in connection with this in 1925 two institutes were created for the reorganization of the Albanian economy, since there was a lack in the banking organization and in the monetary system: necessary conditions to favor foreign capital investments and for the launch of a program for the realization of public works. In exchange for financial support, Mussolini began from 1925 to ask Zog for concessions in the areas where there are oil (petroleum) and agricultural resources; in fact as early as 1913 a scientific mission organized by the Italian Society for the Advancement of Sciences, supported by geologists such as Giorgio Dal Piaz and Antonio de Toni, had found signs of gas, oil and tar sands resources in the Devolli valley and during the war for the first time, the technical offices of the Italian Navy had discovered the bitumen deposits in Selenica and Shushicë, granted these by concession in 1922 by the Albanian government to the Italian mining company of Selenica (SIMSA).

Meanwhile, on January 23, 1923, the new law on Albanian oil concessions came into force; on March 12 and July 15, 1925, two conventions were signed by the Albanian government and the Italian State Railways, according to which the Italian railway received permission to use 164,000 hectares of land in the Devolli valley. The representative company that was created was called AIPA (Azienda Italiana petrol Albania) and started its activity in 1926.

There were many Italian companies that received various concessions for oil, mining, we can mention AMMI (Azienda minerali metalli italiani), SIGL (Societa' italiana giacimenti lignite) that had influence in the area of Korça; SISM (Societa' italo - Albanian mining exploitation) was located in Shkodër; ACAI (Azienda carboni italiani) worked in Mirdita.

During the first years of fascism there was an increase in the activities of societies for agriculture. In 1926, the Italian government entrusted the ONC (Opera

nazionale combattenti) with the task of creating an enterprise to carry out the reclamation and exploitation of agricultural land in Albania. In this way, EIAA (Ente industrie attivita' agrarie) managed to take advantage of the concession of 3000 hectares of agricultural land in the Shjak plain, to receive directly from Albanian producers the production that served for export. Also in the field of fishing, some Italian companies were involved around 1923 and following, in the exploitation of the wealth of Albanian fishing. An important concession was given to the company PESCALBA in 1939. Regarding the use of forests, the Italian-Albanian company SIFA was created, which studied a program for rational cutting and increasing forest areas.

In 1926, a commission was set up with the task of formulating, based on the project worked on in 1923 by the Italian jurist Giulio Menzinger, the final plan for the legislative reform that entered into force in 1928, of the new criminal code that had as a model the code of Zanardelli - t of 1897. On April 1, 1929, the civil code entered into force, which had as legal sources the Italian, French and Swiss civil codes. Also, the military penal code was based on the analogue of the Italian code.

The last code was that of commerce, drawn up on April 1, 1932, where the Italian commercial code of 1882 was used as a basis.

There were also changes in the administrative division, with the division of the territory into 10 prefectures and then into the corresponding sub-prefectures. The placement of the prefect and sub-prefect was the nomenclature of the Minister of Internal Affairs, taken from the analogous way of their selection as in Italy in 1925.

Under these conditions, in 1925, the High Court was established with the same functions as the Court of Cassation in Italy.

Following the historical course, in 1927 an Italian military mission led by Alberto Pariani arrived in Albania, with the task of reorganizing the Albanian army and educating the youth with the creation of the ENGA (Ente nazionale giuventu' Albanese), with the same functions as in Italy.

In the same way as in Italy, the Italian government set up a system of control over the information and culture sectors; fields, which served to show the contribution made by the Italians and the development of the Albanian people. Thus, based on the conventions signed between the two governments, in October 1939, ENIC (Ente nazionale industrie cinematografiche) set up a subsidiary in Albania ENICA (Ente nazionale industrie cinematografiche Albania), where they administered (with an exclusive character) all cinematographic halls, to show spectacles, documentaries produced by LUCE institutes. Also EIAR (Ente italiano audizioni radiofoniche) in 1940 set up a subsidiary in Albania EAAR Ente Albanese audizioni radiofoniche).

⁹ Jorgaqi K., 1992, Sprovë për identifikimin e huazimeve leksikore italiane në shqipen e sotme letrare, Studime Filologjike nr. 1-4, Akademia e Shkencave të Republikës së Shqipërisë, Instituti I Gjuhësisë dhe I Letërsisë, fq 55 - 65

¹⁰ Thomai J., Leksikologjia e gjuhës shqipe, Tiranë 2006, fq 251

¹¹ Po aty

¹² Trani S., L'Unione fra l'Albania e l'Italia Censimento delle fonti (1939-1945) conservate negli archivi pubblici e privati di Roma, 2007, fq 23 – 82, www.archivi.beniculturali.it

The concern of the Italian authorities to justify their presence in Albania, the will to exercise a cultural hegemony and to direct the development of the Albanian intellectual class, led to the instrumentalism of scientific and cultural initiatives. In Albania, with funding from the Minister of Foreign Affairs, the "Skanderbeg" foundation was created, a national entity for cultural growth, consisting of two autonomous sections with different goals, i.e. Italo-Albanian Circolo "Skanderbeg" and the Institute of Albanian Studies. The activities of the Italian archaeological mission also continued; of the association "Dante Aligheri" with the courses of Italian culture and language and of the Italian geographical society, so that through studies they could get to know Albania and the Albanian people more fully.

These extra-linguistic factors enable us to understand more clearly the reasons why Italianisms have penetrated the Albanian language and not only in the terminologies of various fields of knowledge, but also in the language of everyday life. We notice that an important space is devoted to the terminological lexicon, such as in music, mechanical, ecclesiastical, legal, economic, literary, military, etc..

In this context, Dashi B.¹³ highlights some examples for different fields: *ofertor, adorator, konfesional, penitencial, torpedinierë, digë, radë, gondolë, motobarkë, skaf, target, trampolinë, rimorkiator, armator, leva, vira, akostoj, aspirant, karkiaktor, korparmatë, diversi, general, manovër, xhenio, rifuxho, salto, pikiatë, silenciator, breshanë, beretë, pistoletë*. Also in the field of biology and botany *si celulë, virulencë, simbiozë, algë, kamomil karotë, cikore, petal*; in chemistry: *katalizator, dekanton, precipitat, solucion*; in physics: *inerçi, kompensator, kompresor, gjenerator etj*; in geology *vullkan, erosion, aluvion*; in geography: *pol, tropic, continent, krater*; zoology: *balenë, amebë, kamel, kanarinë, gjirafë, fokë, papagall, merluc, acugë, ton, sardele*; in anatomy: *koronar, mukozë, nerv, muskul, tendinë, venë, vertebër*; medicine: *akut, ambulatori, konvaleshencë, konfuzional, kartelë, operoj*; in mathematics: *formulë, spirale, diferencial, kon, ordinatë, paralele, etj*; in mechanics: *bazament, kandelë, kavo, kruskotë, filetë, mandrino, biskotinë, batitor, amortizator, bronzinë, kambio, kavalotë, farfallë, skapamento, paraspruco, serpentinë, spinot etj*; in the economic and financial field: *kapitalizoj, konsumizëm, ofertë, fond, banker, debitor, inkasoj, saldo, obligacion, xhiroj, konvertorj*; në fushën juridike: *imunitet, fiskal, legalizëm, rivendikoj, testament, civilit, abuzoj*; in politics: *centrist, klandestin, agjitacion, liberal, pluralist, deviacion*; in linguistics and literature: *afrikate, kakuminal, barbarizëm, italianizëm, lokucion, kadencë, asonancë, reticencë, stil, novelë, cezurë*; in sports: *kampion, korsi, finale, fintë, forbicatë, markoj, spakatë,*

pankinë; in music: *piano, klavicembalo, korno, mandolin, okarinë, allegro, andante, kreshendo, maestozo, vivace, kanconetë, kantilenë, serenatë, soprano, tenor, mexosoprano*.

We find the traces of many years of relations between Albania and Italy also expressed in the drafting of bilingual dictionaries, which have their beginnings in 1702 with the dictionary of Da Lecce¹⁴. In 1866 the missionary's dictionary Rossi¹⁵ "Vocabolario italiano – epirotico"; dictionary of Buzetit¹⁶ (Busetti); dictionary of Lakalendolas¹⁷ (Lacalendola); dictionary of Kordinjanos¹⁸ (Cordignano) 1938 and characteristic is the inclusion of technical terms specifying the field of use; dictionary of Leotit¹⁹ (Leotti).

One area where the influence of Italianisms is felt is also in military terminology. Especially before the Liberation, it is noticeable that in the field of the army there were deficiencies in the drafting and publication of relevant literature, or it could be very limited and translations from the Italian language were used. Another reason was the preparation of the officer cadre in the Italian academies and in this way they brought both the preparation and the terminological lexicon. Then followed the Italian invasion, which brought an even greater spread of Italianisms in the field of administration, organization, technique and weaponry²⁰.

Conclusions

The Italianisms that have penetrated the Albanian language have been easier to integrate due to the structural proximity of the Italian language to the Albanian language. The lexical categories of the most numerous Italianisms are nouns, adjectives, verbs. We mention the category of gender, which is the same in both Italian and Albanian (masculine gender, feminine gender) where the gender is preserved for the most part, especially in nouns. Word formation is developed in both languages and this serves as an aid for the creation of structural (morphological) calques.

References:

1. **Busetti A.**, 1991, Vocabolario italiano – Albanese, Shkodër
2. **Cipuri H.**, 1989, Zhvillimi i terminologjisë ushtarake pas Çlirimit, Studime mbi leksikon dhe mbi formimin e fjalëve në gjuhën shqipe III, fq 681 – 694
3. **Cordignano F.**, 1938, Dizionario italo-albanese, Shkodër
4. **Çabej E.** 1987, Hyrje në historinë e gjuhës shqipe. Fonetika. Parashtesat-prapashtesat. Shumëzimi I singularizuar, Prishtinë, fq 57
5. **Dashi B.**, 2013, Italianismi nella lingua Albanese, Edizioni Nuova Cultura, Roma
6. **Di Giovine** 2008, Un millennio di storia linguistica albanese: l'influsso lessicale della lingua italo-

¹³ Dashi B., 2013, Italianismi nella lingua Albanese, Edizioni Nuova Cultura, Roma

¹⁴ F. Da Lecce F.M., 1702, fjalori Dittionario italiano – Albanese, Palermo

¹⁵ Rossi, F. P., 1866, Vocabolario epirotico – italiano, Romë

¹⁶ Busetti A., 1991, Vocabolario italiano – Albanese, Shkodër

¹⁷ Lacalendola A., 1936, Dizionario Albanese – italiano, Palo del Colle

¹⁸ Cordignano F., 1938, Dizionario italo-albanese, Shkodër

¹⁹ Leotti A., 1937, Dizionario Albanese – italiano, Roma

²⁰ Cipuri H., 1989, Zhvillimi i terminologjisë ushtarake pas Çlirimit, Studime mbi leksikon dhe mbi formimin e fjalëve në gjuhën shqipe III, fq 681 – 694

iana, "L'Italia dialettale", rivista di Dialettologia italiana, vol LXIX (Serie terza V), Pisa, Edizioni ETS: 107 – 139

7. **F. Da Lecce F.M.**, 1702, fjalori Dittionario italiano – Albanese, Palermo

8. **Jorgaqi K.**, 1995, Italianizma të shqipes standard si ballkanizma, Studime Filologjike, Akademia e Shkencave e Republikës së Shqipërisë, Instituti I Gjuhësisë dhe I Letërsisë nr 1-4, fq 69 – 73

9. **Jorgaqi K.**, 1992, Sprovë për identifikimin e huazimeve leksikore italiane në shqipen e sotme letrare, Studime Filologjike nr. 1-4, Akademia e Shkencave të Republikës së Shqipërisë, Instituti I Gjuhësisë dhe I Letërsisë, fq 55 – 65

10. **Lacalendola A.**, 1936, Dizionario Albanese – italiano, Palo del Colle

11. **Leotti A.**, 1937, Dizionario Albanese – italiano, Roma

12. **Omari A.**, 2009, Vëzhgime rreth zhvillimeve të shqipes së sotme nën ndikimin e gjuhëve të huaja, Gjuha Jonë, Qendra e Studimeve Albanologjike, Instituti I Gjuhësisë dhe I Letërsisë, fq 186

13. **Rossi, F. P.**, 1866, Vocabolario epirotico – italiano, Roma

14. **Trani S.**, L'Unione fra l'Albania e l'Italia Censimento delle fonti (1939-1945) conservate

15. negli archivi pubblici e privati di Roma, 2007, fq 23 – 82, www.archivi.beniculturali.it

16. **Thomai J.**, Leksikologjia e gjuhës shqipe, Tiranë 2006, fq 251